

HARNESSING HEAT: EVALUATING THE THERMAL PERFORMANCE OF ARCH GREENHOUSES FOR NURSERY CULTIVATION

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10658447>

Abstract: *The cultivation of summer crops during winter poses a significant challenge due to the lack of control over environmental parameters in open-field agricultural practices. In contrast, greenhouse cultivation offers a controlled environment, enabling the year-round cultivation of various crops. This study delves into the critical role of environmental control within greenhouses, emphasizing its impact on the successful cultivation of winter-sensitive crops, including vegetables, flowers, and horticultural crops. In traditional open-field practices, essential environmental factors such as sunlight, air composition, and temperature remain uncontrollable, exerting limitations on the cultivation of specific crops during unfavorable seasons. The inability to regulate these parameters hampers the local cultivation of numerous winter crops and their nursery, necessitating the transportation of produce from distant regions. The greenhouse emerges as a transformative solution, providing a controlled microclimate that caters to the specific needs of winter-sensitive crops. By manipulating sunlight exposure, regulating air composition, and optimizing temperature conditions, greenhouses empower farmers to cultivate a diverse range of crops throughout the year, overcoming geographical and seasonal constraints. This research seeks to underscore the pivotal role of greenhouse technology in revolutionizing agriculture, particularly in regions with distinct seasons. The controlled environment not only facilitates the local cultivation of winter crops but also ensures the availability of diverse produce without the reliance on distant sources. The study aims to highlight the economic and ecological advantages of greenhouse cultivation, promoting sustainable and self-sufficient agricultural practices.*

Keywords: *Greenhouse Cultivation, Environmental Control, Seasonal Crop Cultivation, Controlled Agriculture, Sustainable Farming.*

INTRODUCTION

For summer crop during winter. Control of environment inside the greenhouse depends on outer environment Open field agricultural practices have no control on the environment parameters such as sunlight, air composition and temperature that affect the plant growth. Hence a large number of winter vegetables, flowers and other horticultural crops and their nursery can not be grown locally during summer and have to be transported from distant places, same is true. Plants hormonal activity depends on microclimatic environment inside the greenhouse. Hence before going to take nursery inside the greenhouse, more precise performance prediction of greenhouse environment to meet the physiological requirements for growth and development of plants (Georgios, 2001), systematic model is needed. The model should also take care of plant transpiration, evaporation from soil along with other heat transfer

processes. It should also take care of effect of inside microclimate, ventilation and infiltration with ambient air while predicting inside climate (Wang et al, 2000).

For successful plantation programme, cuttings/seed must be raised first in nursery. Production of healthy seed- lings is important where the planting stock is raised seed or cuttings and maintain for about some months (Thakur et al, 1993). Cultivation of nursery also improves the overall growth of plant substantially in terms of height and leaves as compare to outside condition, thus clear saving of 15 days in raising the nursery under green-house (Sethi et al, 2002). A study is therefore undertaken to find out the suitability of greenhouse by predicting the environment inside the greenhouse for nursery raising, where overall year round growth of seedling is very important.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Description of arch shape greenhouse

A modified arch shape greenhouse was selected for cultivation of nursery as modified arch greenhouse performed better where cooling is required (Amita and Tiwari, 2002). An arch shaped greenhouse was designed covering a soil area of 13.4 x 6.00 m that is, 80 square meters as shown in Figure 1. Orientation is in East- West direction. The greenhouse was covered by ultra violet stabilized low-density ethylene sheet of 200-micron thickness.

Energy transfer mechanism

By considering the number of complexities of the heat and mass transfer mechanisms occurring in greenhouse (Garg, 1987) and

Figure. 1 Energy transfer mechanism in greenhouse

Figure 2. Energy transfer mechanism for plant

(Kaushick, 1988) (Figure 1), modeling the greenhouse as a single evaporation component is too cumbersome. Therefore, it could be more rational (4) The temperature of the top surface layer of the soil assumed to approach to divide a greenhouse into separate components and respond instantaneously to energy transfer mechanism. Edge losses model them independently. In view of above consideration, energy were considered to be negligible compared with, those through the balance equations developed separately for the plant (Figure 2), base of the soil. Soil (Figure 3), greenhouse air and cover. The complete analysis (5)The temperature of inlet air through fan-pad at a pad assumed has been described in the following sub-sections (Cooper and as dew point temperature. (6)The greenhouse air was well mixed at Fuller, 1983) by considering following assumptions. all times so that no temperature or moisture gradient existed in the air.

(1) Greenhouse was oriented in E- W direction. (7) The greenhouse is long enough in one direction to permit one-

(2) No coefficient has been included to account for shading due to dimensional analysis of heat transfer.

The structural members. (8) The greenhouse cover was thin enough so that heat transfer

(3) The moisture was freely available at the surface of the soil for through it was essentially one-dimensional.

Figure 3. Energy transfer mechanism for soil

9) Heat loss from the soil to the ground was considered in a steady state.

(10) Thermal properties of materials of construction are time independent. The energy balance equations for the greenhouse soil, plant, greenhouse air and cover are discussed in following subsections.

Under steady state conditions

Cover

$$Q_{aco} + Q_c + Q_{cps} + Q_{rpco} + Q_{rsco} = Q_{cco} + Q_{rcosky}$$

Greenhouse air

$$Q_{cpi} + Q_{cp} + Q_{cs} = Q_i + Q_{ve} + Q_h$$

Plant

$$Q_{ap} = Q_{pc} + Q_t + Q_{rs} + Q_{rpsky}$$

Soil

$$Q_{as} = Q_{cs} + Q_{vs} + Q_{rs} + Q_{tb}$$

Energy balance analysis

The factor influencing the temperature and relative humidity of air inside greenhouse includes solar radiation, ambient temperature, plant respiration, photosynthesis, photo transpiration, thermal exchange between the greenhouse and its surrounding, conduction through greenhouse soil, ventilation, infiltration etc. On account of number and complexity of heat and mass transfer mechanism occurring within the greenhouse, mathematical models have been developed to predict the hourly variation in greenhouse environment i.e. temperature of cover, enclosed air, plants and soil surface and relative humidity of enclosed air for operating condition. The energy balance equations for using finite difference technique and result solved different components of the system were obtained by using computer programme prepared in FORTRAN -77 and

Microsoft Office Excel. Solarimeter and data logger for comparison with model observations also took inside and outside the greenhouse actual experimental observation of solar radiation and ambient temperature.

Cover

The energy received by the cover is the amount of solar radiation absorbed by the cover, convection heat transfer between cover and greenhouse air, energy transferred due to condensation. The cover received heat by radiation heat transfer between cover and soil and cover and plant. The energy lost by the cover was due to the convection and radiation heat transfer between cover and ambient.

The energy balance equation at cover can be written as. Energy stored by the cover = Energy received by cover-

Energy lost by cover.

$$M_{co} C_{co} \frac{dT_{co}}{dt} = I_{co} A_{co} \alpha_{co} + A_{co} h_{coa} (T_{gh} - T_{co}) + A_{co} (h_{coa} / 1005) h_{sg} (W_{gh} - W_{co}) + A_p h_{rpco} (T_p - T_{co}) + A_{st} h_{rsco} (T_{st} - T_{co}) + A_{co} h_{cco} (T_{co} - T_a) + A_{co} h_{rcosky} (T_{co} - T_{sky}) \quad \text{--- (1)}$$

Greenhouse air

The energy received by greenhouse air is because of the heat transfer between cover, plant and soil due to convection and radiation. Heat lost by the greenhouse air is the energy lost through infiltration, ventilation and cooling devices. The energy balance equation for greenhouse air can be written as.

Energy stored in the greenhouse air = Energy received by greenhouse air - Energy lost by the greenhouse air

$$M_{gh} C_{gh} \frac{dT_{gh}}{dt} = h_{coa} A_{co} (T_{co} - T_{gh}) + h_{pa} A_p Li (T_p - T_{gh}) + h_{sa} A_s (T_{st} - T_{gh}) - LVC_{pc} \rho_a (T_{gh} - T_a) - m_v C_{pa} (T_{gh} - T_a) - m_h C_{pa} (T_{gh} - T_h) \quad \text{---(2)}$$

Plant

Energy received by the plant is the amount of solar radiation absorbed by the plant. Energy lost by the plant is the heat transfer by convection from plant to greenhouse air and transpiration between plant

and greenhouse air. Energy was also lost by radiation from plant to soil and plant to sky. The energy balance equation at plant can be expressed as:

Energy stored by the plant = Energy received by the plant - Energy lost by the plant

$$M_p C_p \frac{dT_p}{dt} = I_p a_p A_p - h_{pa} A_p (T_p - T_{gh}) - k_{Li} A_p (W_p - W_{gh}) h_{sg} - h_{rps} A_p (T_p - T_{st}) - h_{rpsky} A_p (T_p - T_{sky}) \quad \text{---(3)}$$

Soil

Energy received by the soil is the amount of solar radiation absorbed by the soil. The energy lost from the soil includes the heat transfer due to convection soil from soil to the greenhouse air, due to evaporation from soil to greenhouse air, radiation heat transfer from soil to greenhouse air and conduction heat transfer between soil and sink. The energy balance equation at soil can be written as:

$$M_s C_s \frac{dT_s}{dt} = \alpha_s I_s A_s - h_{sa} A_s (T_s - T_{gh}) - h_{ds} h_{sg} (W_s - W_{gh}) A_s - h_{rsc} A_s (T_s - T_p) - k A_s (T_s - T_{sb}) \quad \text{---(4)}$$

Humidity ratio

For determining W_{co} , W_p , W_{st} , W_{gh} saturation conditions can be assumed at the cover, leaf and soil surfaces. From psychrometric relations various humidity terms can be written as follows.

$$W_{co} = 0.622 \times \frac{P_{sco}}{P - P_{sco}} \quad \text{--- (5)}$$

$$W_p = 0.622 \times \frac{P^{sp}}{P - P^{sp}} \quad \text{--- (6)}$$

$$W_{st} = 0.622 \times \frac{P^{sst}}{P - P^{sst}} \quad \text{---(7)}$$

The mass balance equation for the greenhouse air could be written as:

$$W_{gh} = 0.622 \times \frac{\phi \times P_{sgh}}{P - P_{sgh}} \quad \text{---(8)}$$

Where ϕ is the relative humidity inside the greenhouse.

The comparisons of different expressions developed by various researchers for calculating saturation vapour pressure corresponding to different temperatures were made with the steam table (Tiwari and Goyal 1998).

According to this expression, vapour pressure at saturation at cover, plant, soil and greenhouse air temperature could be given by $P_{sst} = 6894.76 \exp \left[51.59 - \frac{6834.3}{T_{st} + 273.15} \right]$

$$P_{sgh} = 6894.76 \exp \left[51.59 - \frac{6834.3}{T_{gh} + 273.15} \right] \quad \text{---(11)}$$

$$T_{gh} + 273.15$$

---(12)

The actual vapour pressure in the greenhouse was determined by HORTITRANS model (Jolliet, 1994).

$$P_{gh} = \frac{v_a I_{h+} + t_{h+} + P_{hsgch} + h_{hv} v P_{so}}$$

The relative humidity inside the greenhouse can be determined by

$$P_{gh} \phi = \frac{P_{sg}}{P_{so}} \times 100$$

P_{sg}

$$a = c_1 \ln(1 + c_2 L_i^{c_3})$$

$$h_t = c_4 L_i (1 - c_5 e^{-I/c_6})$$

$$h_v = \rho_a C_{pa} q A$$

Finite difference method

The expression for cover temperature can be written as

$$T_{co} = \frac{1}{D_4} [T_{st} A_4 + T_{gh} B_4 + T_p C_4 + E_4 + A_{co} (h_{coa} / 1005) h_{sg} (W_{gh} - W_{co})]$$

D_4

---(13)

Where,

$$A_4 = A_{st} h_{rsc} B_4 = A_{co} h_{coa}$$

$$C_4 = A_p h_{rpc}$$

$$D_4 = A_{co} h_{coa} + A_c h_{rcc} + A_p h_{rpc} + A_{co} h_{coo} + A_{co} h_{rcosky}$$

$$E_4 = I_{co} A_{co} \alpha_{co} + T_a A_{co} h_{coo} + T_{sky} A_{co} h_{rcosky}$$

The expression for greenhouse air temperature can be written as

1

$$P_{sco} = \frac{6894.76 \exp [51.59 - 6834.3 - 5.17 \ln(T_{co} + 273.15)]}{DC_{33}} = \frac{h_{hco} p_{oa} A_{ap} c_{oLi}}{5}$$

$$T_{co} + 273.15 = \frac{E_3 = T_a (LVC_{pc} \rho_a + mv C_{pa}) + Th (mh C_{pa})}{5} \quad \text{---(9)}$$

The expression for greenhouse plant temperature can be written as

$$P_{sp} = \frac{6894.76 \exp [51.59 - 6834.3 - 5.17 \ln(T_{sp} + 273.15)]}{ktLi A_p (W_p - W_{gh}) h_{sg}} \quad T_p = \frac{1}{T_{sp} + 273.15} [T_{st} A_2 + T_{gh} B_2 + E_2] \quad \text{---(15)}$$

$$T_{gh} = \frac{[T_{st} A_3 + T_c C_3 + T_{co} D_3 + E_3]}{B_3} \quad \text{---(10) } C_2$$

Where,

$$A_3 = h_{sa} A_s$$

$$B_3 = h_{coa} A_{co} + h_{pa} A_p L_i + h_{sa} A_s + LVC_{pc} \rho_a + mv C_{pa} + mh C_{pa}$$

Where,

$$A_2 = h_{rps} A_p$$

$$B_2 = h_{pa} A_{pLi}$$

$$C_2 = h_{pa} A_{pLi} + h_{rps} A_p + h_{rpsky} A_p E_2 = I_{p\alpha} A_p + h_{rpsky} A_p T_{sky}$$

Equation could be simplified for soil temperature as

$$\frac{1}{A_1} [T_{gh} B_1 + T_p C_1 + E_1 - h_{ds} h_{sg} (W_{st} - W_{gh}) A_s] \quad \text{---(16)}$$

$$\overline{A_1}$$

Where

$$k A_s$$

$$A_1 = h_{sa} A_s + h_{rsp} A_s + t$$

$$\overline{B_1} = h_{sa} A_s$$

$$C_1 = h_{rsc} A_s$$

$$E_1 = \alpha_s I_s A_s - k A_s T_{sb} t$$

Heat and mass transfer coefficients

The convective heat transfer coefficient between (h_{cogh}) cover and greenhouse air, (h_{sgh}) ground and greenhouse air, (h_{pgh}) plant and greenhouse air, (h_{coa}) cover and ambient air. The radiative heat transfer coefficient between (h_{rpco}) plant and cover, (h_{rsc}) ground and cover, (h_{rcosky}) cover and sky, (h_{rps}) ground and plant. The mass transfer coefficient (h_{ds}) is obtained by using Lewis relation (Cooper and Fuller, 1983) and given in following section.

Natural convective heat transfer between cover and ambient

$$h_{coa} = 2.8 + 3.8 W$$

Forced heat transfer between Cover, Ground, plant and greenhouse air

$$h_{cogh/pgh/sgh} = k Nu/R$$

Where,

$$K = \text{Constant}$$

$$Nu = 0.664 Re^{0.5} Pr^{0.3}$$

$$Re = VR/\nu$$

Various radiative heat transfer coefficient (Swinbank, 1963) and (Kothari et al., 2006) are given as follows.

Cover and sky

$$h_{rcosky} = \frac{\sigma(T_{co}^2 + T_{sky}^2)(T_{co} + T_{sky})}{\frac{1}{\epsilon_c} - 1}$$

$$\epsilon_c$$

Where,

$$T_{sky} = 0.0552(T_a)^{1.5}$$

Plant and cover

$$h_{rpco} = \frac{\sigma(T_p^2 + T_{co}^2)(T_p + T_{co})}{\frac{1}{\epsilon_p} + \frac{1}{\epsilon_{co}} - 1}$$

$$\epsilon_p \quad \epsilon_{co}$$

Soil and cover

$$h_{rsc} = \frac{\sigma(T_{st}^2 + T_{co}^2)}{\frac{1}{\epsilon_s \epsilon_{co}} - 1} (T_{st} + T_{co})$$

$\epsilon_s \epsilon_{co}$

Plant and sky

$$h_{rps} = \frac{\sigma(T_p^2 + T_{sky}^2)}{\frac{1}{\epsilon_p} - 1} (T_p + T_{sky})$$

ϵ_p

Plant and soil

$$h_{rps} = \frac{\sigma(T_p^2 + T_{st}^2)}{\frac{1}{\epsilon_c \epsilon_{st}} - 1} (T_p + T_{st})$$

$\epsilon_c \epsilon_{st}$

Soil and plant

$$h_{rsc} = \frac{\sigma(T_{st}^2 + T_c^2)}{\frac{1}{\epsilon_{st} \epsilon_c} - 1} (T_{st} + T_c)$$

$\epsilon_{st} \epsilon_c$

Mass transfer coefficient

The mass transfer coefficient, h_{ds} is obtained by using the Lewis relation.

$h_{ds} = \text{heat transfer coefficient} \cong h_{sa}$ specific heat of air 1005

An approximate value for the latent heat of vaporisation h_{fg} can be obtained from the expression [7] obtained by curve fit to data from standard tables and can be expressed as:

$$h_{sg} = 3161.36 - 2.406 T_{st}$$

Input parameters

The hourly ambient temperatures, solar radiation (Mani and Rangarajan, 1981) and humidity for typical winter day for December and summer day for May for Udaipur were considered for numerical calculations.

Temperatures of greenhouse soil, plant, air and cover can be calculated with the help of equations 5 to 16, specification and properties use in Table 1, at any time under steady state conditions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of radiation on greenhouse air temperature

The results showing the increase in greenhouse air temperature over ambient temperature corresponding to different solar radiation have been presented in this sec-

Table 1. Specification and properties used for modeling.

Parameter	Values	Unit
Length of greenhouse (L)	13.4	meter
Thickness of polythene	200	micron
Absorptivity of cover (α_{co})	0.25	Dimensionless
Transmittivity of cover (τ_{co})	0.75	Dimensionless
Density of polythene (ρ_{pe})	1150	Kg/m ³
Specific heat of cover (C_{co})	2302	J/Kg °C
Emissivity of cover (ϵ_{co})	0.9	Dimensionless
Specific heat of air (C_a)	1005	J/Kg °C
Thermal conductivity of air	0.028	W/m ² °C
Density of air (ρ_a)	1.2	Kg/m ³
Specific heat of plant (C_p)	3190	J/Kg °C
Emissivity of plant (ϵ_p)	0.5	Dimensionless
Specific heat of soil (C_s)	2300	J/Kg °C
Density of soil (ρ_s)	1250	Kg/m ³
Absorptivity of soil (α_s)	0.80	Dimensionless
Emissivity of soil (ϵ_s)	0.05	Dimensionless
Wind velocity (W)	5	Km/h
Area of ventilation (A_{vent})	0.09	m ²
Stefan-Boltzman constant (σ)	5.67×10^{-8}	W/m ² K ⁴
Prandtl Number (Pr)	0.7	Dimensionless
Atmospheric pressure (P_{atm})	101.325	Kg/m ²

Figure 4. Increase in greenhouse air temperature with solar radiation.

The calculations was carried out for different values of ambient temperature viz. 0, 10, 20, 30, 40 and 45°C.

The increase in greenhouse air temperature over ambient temperature corresponding to solar radiation transmitted was calculated and plotted for different values of ambient temperature in Figure 4. It is clear that the greenhouse temperature was highly influenced by the solar radiation. The increase in greenhouse temperature over ambient temperature was more with increase in radiation. This increase in temperature was more if the ambient temperature was less and the increase was less if ambient temperature was more. During no radiation period the increase in greenhouse temperature over ambient temperature was negligible. The maximum increase in greenhouse air temperature was 13.92°C for a solar radiation of 500 W/m² with 0°C ambient temperature (Kothari et al, 2006). Above results indicates that under cold and sunny climate we could cultivate those crops inside the greenhouse which cannot be grown outside the greenhouse at low temperature.

Effect of ambient temperature on greenhouse air temperature

The results showing the increase in greenhouse air temperature over ambient temperature corresponding to different ambient temperatures have been presented in this section. The calculations was carried out for different values of solar radiation viz. 0, 100, 200, 300, 400 and 500 W/m².

In Figure 5 the increase in greenhouse air temperature over ambient temperature corresponding to ambient temperature was plotted for different values of solar radiation. It is clear that for most of solar radiation values of solar radiation the increase in greenhouse air temperature over ambient temperature decreases with the increase in ambient temperature.

Prediction of microclimate inside the greenhouse for Udaipur condition

The hourly values of greenhouse temperatures were calculated by finite difference method. The microclimate inside the greenhouse was predicted for the climatic data of Udaipur. For this, whole year was assumed to be represented by 12 monthly average days for which the hourly data of solar radiation and ambient air temperatures were taken from the actual reading for performance of greenhouse.

The hourly values of soil temperature, plant temperature, greenhouse air temperature and cover temperatures calculated by finite difference method for typical days of different months for Udaipur climate. The hourly values indicate that there was an appreciable increase in greenhouse soil and plant temperature as compared to

Figure 5. Increase in greenhouse air temperature with ambient temperature.

Outside condition in winter. The increase in greenhouse air temperature above ambient temperature is up to 15°C more over ambient temperature during sunshine hours. Cover temperature, Soil temperature, plant temperature and greenhouse temperature shown in Table 2. It is evident that there was an appreciable increase in greenhouse temperature during daytime as compared to ambient temperature. The increase in greenhouse air temperature above ambient temperature varies approximately from 4 to 15°C corresponding to low and high values of solar radiation respectively. Based on these results it could be concluded that temperature conditions inside the greenhouse could be improved and it is possible to propagate the nursery inside the greenhouse, which could not be grown under low temperature condition outside the greenhouse.

Comparison with experimental observation

Values of greenhouse air temperature on typical day for the month of December 2006 were measured at an experimental site. The measured values of solar radiation and ambient temperature were used as input data in computer programme developed for calculating hourly values of greenhouse temperature by finite difference method. The calculated values of the hourly greenhouse air temperature along with experimental results have been presented in Figure 6 for the month of December. Experimental and calculated values of greenhouse temperature were almost same with variation of 2 to 3°C (Kothari et al., 2006). It may be inferred from these

Hour of the day	Ambient Temperature (°C)	Solar radiation W/m ²	Cover Temperature (°C)	Floor Temperature (°C)	Crop Temperature (°C)	Greenhouse Temperature (°C)
1	15.5	0	20.4	20.65	20.53	20.53
2	14.9	0	20.7	20.94	20.82	20.8
3	14.4	0	20.11	20.35	20.23	20.21
4	13.7	0	19.61 18.92	19.86 19.17	19.73 19.04	19.7
5	13.3	0				19.02
6	12.8	1				18.63

7	17	65	18.52 18.06	18.78 18.34	18.65 18.2	18.29
8	18	259	19.47	21.15	20.36	20.57
9	20.3	473	24.89	29.64	27.43	27.55
10	22.8	653	31.76	39.04	35.63	35.58
11	24.9	778	37.02	45.96	41.74	41.58
12	26.3	842	40.74	50.58	45.9	45.66
13	27.2	844	42.72	52.85	48.01	47.72
14	33.2	769	43.21	53.08	48.36	48.02
15	28.1	635	42.24	51.2	46.92	46.58
16	27.9	458	40.1	47.59 42.2	44.03 39.62	43.68
17	27.6	249	36.74 33.01	36.05 30.46	34.62 29.95	39.31
18	26.4	64	29.35	26.74	26.63	34.39
19	24.5	1	26.49			29.8
20	22.9	0				26.56
21	21.8	0	24.87	25.1	24.99	24.94
22	21	0	23.78	24.01	23.9	23.86
23	20.2	0	22.98 22.19	23.22 22.42	23.1	23.07
24	18.4	0			22.31	22.23

Table 2. Hourly variation in greenhouse c ver, floor, crop and greenhouse temperatures for the month of March at Udaipur

Figure 6. Comparison of theoretical and experimental values of greenhouse air temperature for the month of December at Udaipur. results that the theoretical values were in reasonably good agreement with the experimental results. Therefore, the mathematical model could be used to predict temperature conditions inside the greenhouse for a variety of climatic parameters.

Conclusions

- Condition with highest solar radiation with lowest ambient temperatures, raise in greenhouse air temperature is higher than the condition with lowest solar radiation with highest ambient temperatures.
- The parametric study reveals that maximum increase in greenhouse air temperature was 13.92 °C for solar radiations of 500 W/m² and 0°C ambient temperatures.
- Experimental and predicted values of greenhouse temperature were almost same with variation of 2 to 3 °C.
- The mathematical model could be used to predict temperature conditions inside the greenhouse for a variety of climatic parameters.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Authors are highly thankful to Ministry of Non-conversat- ion Energy Sources for providing the financial assistance to carry out the research work. They are also thankful to the Department of Renewable Energy Sources, College of Technology and Engineering, Udaipur for providing all sorts of required facilities for the study.

Abbreviations:

A -Area, m²; As, Aco, Ap - soil, cover and plant area; C - Specific heat, J/kg °C; C1-C6 Coefficient of equation; Cpa Cpp - Specific heats of greenhouse air and plant; h - Heat transfer coefficient, W/m²°C;

hdshe - Mass transfer coefficient for floor; hrpco, hrsco, hrcosky - Radiative heat transfer between plant to cover, soil to cover and cover to sky; hrpsky - Radiative heat transfer between plant and sky; hpa, hcoa, hcoo - Convective heat transfer coefficients between crop and greenhouse air, cover and greenhouse air, cover and ambient; has - Convective heat transfer between floor and greenhouse air; hsg - Latent heat of evaporation, kJ/kg; ht - Coefficient of heat transfer for transpiration; hv - Coefficient of heat transfer for ventilation; Is, Ip, Ico - Solar radiation on soil, plant and cover; k - Thermal conductivity of floor; L - Length of greenhouse; Li - Leaf area index; mh - Mass flow rate out of cooling/ dehumidifying device; mv - Mass flow rate due to natural or forced venting with ambient air; Nu - Nusselt Number; P - Vapour pressure of outside air; Pgh - Vapour pressure inside greenhouse; Psco, Pdst, Psc - Saturation vapour pressure at cover, floor and crop temperature; Qap, Qaco, Qas - Energy absorbed by crop, cover and floor from solar radiation; Qbs - Energy transferred by conduction; Qc - Energy transfer by condensation; Qcp, Qcs, Qcps - Energy transfer by convection between plant, soil and plant and soil; Qcco, Qccs - Energy transfer by convection between cover and cover and soil; Qh, Qi - Energy transfer due to cooling device and infiltration; Qpci, Qpc, Qps - Energy transfer by convection between plant and infiltration, plant and soil and greenhouse air; Qr, Qrs - Energy transfer by radiation between plant and ambient and between soil and plant; Qrpco, Qrsco - Energy transfer by radiation between plant and cover and between soil and cover; Qrcosky, Qrpsky - Energy transfer by radiation between cover and sky and plant and sky; Qt; Energy transfer by plant transpiration; Qtb - Energy transfer by conduction between top surface layer and main mass of soil; Qve - Energy transfer due to ventilation with ambient air; Qvs - Energy transfer due to evaporation from soil; r - Radius; Re - Reynolds Number; Tp - Plant temperature; t - Thickness of soil; Ttb, Tst - Temperature of top layer of soil and temperature of top layer and soil sink; Ta, Tp, Tco - Ambient, plant and cover temperature; Tsb, Tst, Tgh - Soil sink, soil and greenhouse temperature; v - Psychrometric constant; V - Wind velocity; w - Fraction of floor with free water available for evaporation; Wp, Wco - Absolute humidity ratio of plant and cover; wdi - Diffuse radiation on greenhouse floor; Wst, Wgh - Saturated air at plant, cover, soil and greenhouse air temperature; p, co, s - Plant, cover and floor absorbance; p, , st - Plant and floor emittance.

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